

VERB WORD GROUP AND SEMANTIC CLASSIFICATION PROBLEMS IN IT

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Abstract: In this article, we analyze the verb phraseology and its semantic classification issues, and express our opinions.

Key words: language, semantics, classification principle, grammatical essence of the verb, grammatical category, grammatical structure, verb, structural classification, grammatical classification, meaning-relations.

When we talk about the grammatical nature of the verb, it can be noted that the verb is one of the main word groups and differs from other word groups by its meaning, grammatical forms and syntactic functions. A verb connects action, presence, state, and relationship with reality in a process-like manner, defining it in terms of time. It is by this feature that the verb differs from the noun it is derived from.

The verb is one of the active word groups in all languages. The semantic scope of the verb is wide, but mainly it means a situation that gives the idea of action and action. The learning of the verb word group is inextricably linked to other word groups. The largest group of words is also a verb. Mahmoud Zamakhshari, who was born in Khorezm, wrote several works on linguistics. The work "Muqaddimat-ul Adab" consists of five parts, in the form of nouns, verbs, connectives, noun changes, verb changes. Created. Zamakhshari was the first scientist to group verbs according to their stem. Zamakhshari's place in the study of morphology is incomparable. One of the important written sources in the study of the history of the formation of the old Uzbek literary language, the work "Tafsir" contains a lot of words belonging to the verb group and used in various forms. Together with the aspects specific to the old Uzbek language, aspects related to the language of the ancient Turkic times are also shown. The grammatical meanings of person, number, tense and mood are expressed in the verb forms mentioned in the work.

In this work, full and shortened forms of verbs are used, and detailed information about the word group of verbs is given. The work "Muhabbatnama", which contains all-Turkish features, was noted by our scholars as an example of the old Uzbek written literary language. Indeed, several morphological features are noted in the work. We can know this from the given information about the verb phrase. Some of the verb forms in "Muhabbatnama" correspond to the old Uzbek language. But the grammatical devices used in some verb forms are characteristic of the language of much earlier periods.

In the 14th century, there are two other works whose author is unknown, the first of which is the dictionary "Translator". This dictionary consists of 76 pages and consists of four parts. The first part is devoted to the name, the second part is devoted to the issue of verb tense and action noun, the third part is to the type and declension, and the fourth part is to the use of the word. The first three parts of this work are devoted to morphology, and mainly the verb word family is studied. 8 The second work is the work "At-tuhfa", which also has a very extensive

study of the verb family. is given. The categories of the verb ratio, participle-infinitive, person, mood, and tense will be covered in detail. This work reflects on the relationship between the unknown, togetherness, addition, and identity.

A peculiarity of English verbs is that, in addition to semantic verbs, as in Russian, there are modal and auxiliary verbs, linking verbs, which are usually not translated in any way, but have additional semantic carries a load. One of the unique features of English verbs is that they can be regular or irregular. Irregular verbs differ from regular verbs in that the past tense is formed by adding the suffix -.

You should use dictionaries, textbooks and a special table available on the Internet to find out what form an irregular verb has in the past or future tense.

Another feature of English verbs is the presence of personal and impersonal verbs. Personal verbs act as a predicate in a sentence whenever there is a subject. Impersonal verbs include participles, for example. They rarely act as a predicate, they perform the functions of the rest of the sentence.

The distinctive features of English verbs include the way they are formed. There are simple, complex and derived verbs. Simple ones consist only of the root and the ending of the word, for example, hit - hit. Compound verbs are formed by adding the roots of words, for example, to grow - to grow. Derived verbs contain additions and suffixes in addition to the root. Example: dislike - dislike.

When learning English, you should devote a lot of time to the verb to be, which is already a characteristic in itself. It performs four functions, most often it plays the role of a semantic verb and a linking verb. Any sentence in English cannot be made without a verb, so to exist exists where there is no semantic verb and there is a compound nominal predicate, for example, I am a student, in Russian " "I am a student" is translated.

English also has modal verbs. They are given special attention because these parts of speech differ from other English verbs in a number of features. They are indicators of the characteristic of action and are used together with semantic verbs. For example, a modal verb must express a request to perform an action. I go to school - I go to school. I have to go to school - I have to go to school.

Modal verbs never have the endings -ing, -s and -es. In some cases, modal verbs can be replaced by their equivalents or equivalent universal verbs. Equivalents are usually used instead of modal verbs in the past and future tenses.

Equivalent universal verbs, in addition to the modal function, can be performed by others, including semantic ones. For example, to allow is translated as "to allow, to allow" and can replace the verb may. Also, modal verbs are used without auxiliary verbs and with a particle.

As a conclusion, we can say that our scientists have been working on the verb phraseology since ancient times. Until now, this phrase is being analyzed in depth and news is being introduced. Verb vocabulary is a very broad topic. No group of words can be imagined without a group of verbs. The center of the sentence is the participle, and the participle is mainly expressed by the verb. That is why the verb forms the main content of the sentence. This phrase has been the cause of many debates and discussions, and is being studied by scientists to this day.

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